

THE INFLUENCE OF INNOVATIVE PROCESSES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY: A SYNERGETIC APPROACH

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Abstract: This article discusses the impact of innovative processes on the development of innovative activities and the role and importance of a synergistic approach in the management of innovative processes.

Key words: Synergetic, ontological, chaos, nonlinear, dissipative, technology, innovations.

The synergetic approach not only changes the management strategy of society as a whole, but also makes it possible to look at the problem of management of innovation processes in a new way by focusing on their social mechanisms and ontological foundations. It is the lack of knowledge about the features of the innovation process, as well as the insufficient study of all the factors affecting its progress, that leads to failure, for example, if the products of scientific organizations do not find manufacturers and users. In the conditions of a market economy, this type of failure usually has a significant cost. Knowing the characteristics of the innovation process allows to avoid various unfavorable situations when innovative activities do not achieve the set goals: the intended change does not occur in the specified volume or in rare cases does not occur at all.

What are the main features of this complex process, which connects different areas of social life, such as science, technology, production and, finally, the market? They are often determined by the nature of innovations, which on the one hand have characteristics characteristic of scientific and research developments, and on the other hand belong to production with their related aspects. Therefore, they should be related to all requirements related to rational cognitive activity, as well as production-economic activity.

Innovative processes have an objective character and are determined by the logic of the development of welfare-producing forces (that is, by socio-economic laws), as well as by natural and scientific laws. It is the laws that determine the synergistic nature of innovative activity. In this sense, the innovative process is similar to creativity (it is usually included in its initial stages) because in both cases self-organization - the processes of the next stages cannot be carried out without their participation. In order to describe this basis,

in our opinion, it is necessary to use "typical synergistic" concepts such as "chaos" and "order". In contrast to classical rationality, "chaos" in synergetics is able to communicate at different levels and lead to the formation of a new structure, as a result of which it appears as a constructive mechanism of evolution (in which several types of chaos are formed in synergetics: balanced, dynamic, turbulent, turbulent and statistics).

"Chaos" appears as an intrinsic property of a nonlinear dynamical system, in almost all systems, and always in systems with a large number of degrees of freedom, as well as in small-scale systems, as modern research shows. "Chaos, according to V.I. Arshinov and V.G. Budanov, exists everywhere, and if we do not focus on it in the same form all the time - especially if we do not pay attention to it as an internal feature of a dynamic system, then we only have a certain perspective, a sufficient level of parameters. we observe from the point of view of a narrow area (for example, in the area of the bifurcation point) or it is invisible on large time scales (in the case of the motion of the planets of the solar system).

Dynamic chaos exposes the system to the outside world. It is in the chaotic evolutionary phase that it becomes possible to perceive, receive information from an external source, and harmonize the system with external conditions. In this sense, the creative, creative beginning is embodied in this place. Chaos is the desired degree of order. It allows breaking fixed stereotypes in observation as well as activity. In this case, due to the subjectivity of its implementation, both in creativity and in the innovative process, due to the fact that it is intended for the final product, self-organization is supplemented with organization, and it soon plays the role of an initiator.

The complexity of the management of innovation processes, in most cases, is related to the difficulties in the analysis of the emergence of something new. In order to create an innovation with certain parameters that can satisfy some need, experts need to know whether it exists or not. In other words, it is necessary to find such a form of being in the composition of this known reality, which does not exist in this being, and which represents the possibility of this being. It is both within and without itself.

The creative ability of some people and groups working in one or another innovative cycle covers various conflicts that support them, as well as objective reality. This conflict can be solved on the basis of synergetic methodology, which is one of the main concepts of nonlinearity. Nonlinearity is an essential aspect of

dynamic cooperative systems that evolves and is a universal and fundamental edge of the surrounding reality.

The non-linear approach to the evolutionary process is related to the formation of new qualities and characteristics, the phenomenon of leaping. The fact that non-linear elements cannot be eliminated makes the world fundamentally uncertain and completely controllable and predictable. Such an approach fundamentally changes many long-standing ideas of humanity, because in this case the world appears not as a mechanism, but as a self-organizing organism.

Considering the emergence of new qualities in non-linear processes, synergetics allowed to face the innovative process from a new perspective. Innovations are studied not only from the point of view of human activity (manifested through social mechanisms), but also in the broad fundamental context of innovative processes, in general as one of the forms of "gross renewal of matter in the world" (V. Nikolko).

In this respect, there is almost no scientific research devoted to the consideration of innovation. Perhaps the reason for this is embodied in the fact that in modern philosophical circles, in general, insensitivity to innovative problematics is defined without any reason to fear reductionism. This is also possible within the framework of synergetic concepts, in which their representatives forget the existence of the opposite effect on the structure, thereby denying the structural-functional dialectic.

It is known that self-organization in systems of different levels has its own special aspects. Innovation in innovative processes does not appear as in natural systems, but is developed by special means, combined with the free activity of its creators within the framework of determinations in action. Here we are talking about the non-linear process of probabilistic determination carried out through social mechanisms. Such an approach helps to form a new methodological principle of research.

In order to explain the emergence of innovations both in nature and in social systems, a general scheme that is considered invariant for different levels can be used: self-organization can begin only in systems that are far from open non-equilibrium dynamic equilibrium. Dissipation plays an important role in this.

E.E. Knyazeva, S.P. Kurdyumov consider dissipation to be the most important factor in the self-development of the world, because without it, a new organization will not appear by itself. In an open self-developing system, there is

a struggle between two opposing principles: those who create structures that increase uncertainty in the overall environment and those that diffuse uncertainties of various natures:

If the second base is stronger than the first, no new structures will appear. Dissipative processes are the basis of creation of chaos, at the micro level they are a special manifestation of the self-organizing tendencies of the nonlinear environment as a guiding force that dissolves into the attractor. Fluctuations, that is, random effects on the system, are also important in the process of self-organization. It can be noted that self-organization begins with the process of fluctuation.

If changes in the system reach the limits of stability, stability may be lost, and the system cannot be described by deterministic (linear) equations, and the system cannot be controlled. Because it can develop towards different modes of operation. This is a point of bifurcation, in which random factors increase and the next stages of development of events cannot be predicted in advance, or as they say, a "map of possibilities", a whole field opens, it is a point of qualitative or catastrophic change of the system, a new point of development.

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